

MOTIVATING ELEMENTARY SCHOOL LEARNERS TO ENGLISH WITH THE HELP OF SELECTED HANDBOOK CONTENT

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Abstract:

The article explores the topic of students' motivation and course books, that is how the content of the course books influence students' motivation, but also how the teachers use the course books and teachers books in the classroom. The two-way research, aimed at finding answers to the main research questions, was based on the specially prepared survey conducted among teachers, but also on the (indicated by the investigated teachers as the most usable) course-book analysis.

Keywords: handbook, course-book contents, motivation, motivation techniques

1. Introduction

In many European schools the main tool when teaching English is a course book. However, following the teachers' opinion (Werbińska, in Pawlak, 2014), it is often difficult to find an appropriate course book, i.e. the one which could not only fulfil learners' needs and preferences but also help motivate the students to study English in the best possible way. As the issues presented above do not seem to be easily grasped by many teachers and/or researchers, it should be stated what is to be understood by this form of motivation and how (and what) course-book contents can be expected to help motivate language students.

2. Motivation and foreign language student motivating procedures

If it comes to the definition of motivation, Harmer (2001), observes that motivation can help one explain why people decide to do particular things, how much they are into such activities and how long they plan to continue doing any of them. Another definition, this time offered by Dörnyei (2001) states that motivation not only illustrates human voluntary involvement in an activity, but also it defines the amount of time one

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has decided to be [deeply] involved in a procedure selected by them. In other words, the more people are motivated, the more they are willing to do something. If their motivation is low, the chance to succeed is respectively lower.

Researches carried out in order to explore the issue of motivation allowed to discover a considerable number of motivational theories, five of them will remain in the sphere of interest while writing this paper; these are mostly classical ones: Hull's (1943) drive theory, Lewin's (1939) field theory, Atkinson's (1965) theory of achievement strivings, the attribution theory proposed by Heider, Kelley & Weiner (in Kelley, 1967) and, finally, Rotter's (1966) social learning theory. All of them will be presented from the analytical point of view, in many cases shared with Deci & Ryan's (1985) approach to motivation and motivation-resulting, as well as affect-based human behaviour. In the first theory, the concept of instinct was replaced by the notion of drive, so that it was assumed that organism acts when it feels the need and the lack of satisfaction. In the next (Lewin's) one, one could read that performance is determined by the person and the environment and that, subsequently, the motivational force which acts on the person is controlled by tension, valence and psychological distance of the person from a goal. At the same time, Atkinson's theory of achievement stated that a likelihood to achieve a goal depends on three factors: the need for achievement, the probability that one will be successful at the task and the incentive values of success. While studying the theory, proposed by Heider et al., one could find out that an individual's causal attributions of achievement affects their behaviour and motivation, both of them being the two immediate results of one's will to perform. Additionally, one of the main principles found in this theory assumes that people tend to interpret their environment so as to maintain a positive self-image. Finally, the last concept we are interested in, created by Rotter (1966) says that motivation is a function of expectancy, which is determined by one's past experiences in the specific situation, and reinforcement, that refers to "the degree of preference for any reinforcement". (Rotter in Graham & Weiner, 1996, p. 3). All these theories were paid attention to while construing the research model applied in the research presented below.

Apart from these general theories of motivation, there should also be mentioned more specified contemporary motivation constructs. Following the description offered by Graham & Weiner (1996) they can be roughly divided into two groups: the constructs connected with one's ability of self-perception, among which one can distinguish such issues as self-worth, self-efficacy and learned helplessness; and the constructs linked with various achievement goals, such as: task involvements vs. ego involvement), intrinsic vs. extrinsic incentives as well as a number of cooperative, competitive and individualistic goal structures.

The initial three ones are concentrated on the appearance of a new stream in the field of motivation, that is the study of the self. The first of them is a self-worth construct, which was created by Covington (1992); according to the issue, people are motivated by the need to perceive themselves as competent, what briefly means that a feeling of personal worth comes out from one's conviction of personal ability to do

something. It is important to observe this assertion from the perspective of a language learner as well as the oncoming fluctuation of their growing (or falling) momentary levels of motivation while working with given linguistic segments.

Related with the above, the construct of self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief about their capabilities to perform well. It was propagated by Bandura (1991), who underlined the motivational role of self-efficacy, stating that students' self-efficacy beliefs largely control their current levels of motivation. Here again, the picture of a foreign language learner is never to be lost sight of; following Ur (2007) the more self-efficient such a learner is, the better and faster the whole process of foreign language education can proceed.

In contrast to self-efficacy, there stands the construct of learned helplessness, as it is always connected with one's personal feeling of mental/physical inability. It usually appears after the students' repetitive failures, giving vent to the sudden growth of the feeling that they are not capable of improving their results (what effectively keeps away them from trying to succeed, thus increasing the loss of self-esteem).

The other three (contrastive in themselves) constructs mentioned above are related to the achievement goals. The first of them, task vs. ego involvement, entails two contrasting approaches. As Nicholls (1984 in: Graham & Weiner, 1996) explains, the former is characterised by a state when one's goal is to master the task, whereas in the latter situation, the most important is either to demonstrate high ability closely related to the level of vigour observed in others, or to disguise one's low ability to perform a task in some other way. While observing this construct in a classroom setting, one cannot avoid thinking about the clearly convergent behaviour of classroom pupils who do not volunteer to answer a question asked by their teacher only because of their strong feeling they have to stand united with the rest of the class.

Intrinsic versus extrinsic incentives are related to the motivation research results which show that schooling weakens our natural (i.e. intrinsic) will to learn and - apart from that - is responsible for the development of extrinsic motivation throughout offering students different kinds of rewards. Therefore, students are less interested in the tasks which become not truly enjoyable for them.

Cooperative, competitive and individualistic goal structures are the three types of incentive structures described by Deutsch (in Graham & Weiner, 1996) that base on students' group work. The first one, i.e. the cooperative construct, appears when two or more students are rewarded as a group. If it comes to the competitive goal structure, it occurs when two or more students are compared with each other, and the one assessed as the best is rewarded. Finally, the last, that is individualistic, construct is to be observed when individuals are rewarded for their own work, not taking into consideration results of other learners.

When it comes to the question what motivates students, the answer can be sought in a number of theories that directly focus upon various explanatory reasons concerning this issue. Dailey (2009) produces as comparative list of quite a few of them. In this way, students can be motivated by the following concerns.

Gardner and Lambert (1959) proposed that motivation to foreign (in their research called second) language learning depends on one's positive attitude towards the target language community and the will of belonging to that society; such form of behaviour can be called integrative motivation, as it most often occurs when the students want to learn the target language because of their need of belonging to the target language culture.

One more factor resulting in the appearance of intrinsic motivation is the enjoyment of learning, which students should feel in order to be motivated. It appears when we want to do something just for ourselves, not taking into consideration any whatsoever external factors.

The next aspect which has been found to be motivating for students is the individual's image of their future self, (often called the ideal self) which involves both instrumental as well and integrative qualities. It means that students are triggered to act, by the vision of how their knowledge will change (and influence) their future.

There are also quite a few external pressures that motivate students to learn the target language. Among them there are desires to please parents or teachers and get the grades they will be satisfied with, to receive a reward or to fulfil some pragmatic goal. As it seems, the key issue for teachers is how to awaken in the students the first three factors mentioned above, avoiding the awakening of the fourth one at the same time.

This is because the former three act positively on the students and result in the real need of learning the target language, whereas the latter is temporal only (what means that after leaving the school or completing the language course, the pressures from the outside are no more valid and motivating for them).

An interesting student-motivating concept has been launched by Williams & Burden (1997, in: Dörnyei, 2001), who proposed a framework of motivational components which were grouped according to their motivational strength, whether it is internal or external.

Among the internal factors there were distinguished some interesting aspects connected with activity, some of them being one's intrinsic interest, perceived value of activity, or the concept of topic mastery. The first one was related to the arousal of curiosity and optimal degree of difficulty. Another issue specified above was the perceived value of activity which entails a number of items such as: whether it is relevant to the students' personality, the quality of the expected outcomes, as well as its intrinsic value. Subsequently, we can find there factors connected with the sense of agency as locus of causality and control, but also one's ability to set accurate goals. The next item involves the concept of mastery and regards one's feeling of competence, as well as one's awareness of developing skills and self-efficacy. It is interconnected with self-concept, which – by the way - also concerns the issue of the self of students. Thus, it pertains to the awareness of one's own skills, what are students' weak and strong points, how they perceive their successes and failures and therefore how they judge their self-worth and, last but not least, whether they experience the helplessness. Most of the internal factors specified above are related to students' attitudes towards

language learning in general, the target language but also the target language community and culture. Apart from them, the researchers also list other factors which have influence on motivation, that is the affective states like confidence, anxiety and fear but also physical ones, such as developmental age and/or gender.

In contrast to the internal factors, Williams and Burden (1997) also propose a list of external factors. One of these are significant others, i.e. parents, teachers and peers who play the crucial role in creating students' motivation and often become authorities for them. In this light the nature of interaction between them and the students should be considered: what are the mediated learning experiences, whether students receive appropriate feedback, whether the significant others apply rewards, punishments and sanctions. What is also recognized as important for the students' motivation is their learning environment, i.e. whether they feel comfortable, what resources are used, the period of time the learning takes place, the size of class and/or the type of school. In terms of broader context, the researchers specify such issues as wider family networks, the local educational system, conflicting interests, cultural norms and societal expectations and attitudes are the factors which can be influential.

A number of researchers (Harmer, 1998; Huit, 2001 and many others) recognize the motivational function teachers perform in the classroom. Huitt (2001), for example, proposes a list of particular activities which can influence learners' motivation (both extrinsic and intrinsic) in the classroom environment. At the same time, however, the researcher underlines that teachers should focus mostly on intrinsic suggestions, remembering that they may not appear motivating for all students. The list of intrinsic suggestions contains such items like: teachers should explain or show why a particular content or skill is important for the learners; they should also be able to create and maintain curiosity, provide a variety of activities and sensory stimulations, provide games and stimulations, set goals for learning, relate learning to the students' needs and, finally, help students develop planned activities.

Huit (2001) also points out that extrinsic suggestions will work as long as the teacher controls the students. The list of extrinsic suggestions prepared here entails such issues like: the teacher should provide clear expectations, give corrective feedback, provide valuable rewards and make them available.

Dörnyei (in Macaro, 2003) suggests ten instructions for motivating a language learner. Among them there can be found an observation that teachers are supposed to set a personal example with their own behaviour, what practically means that any theoretical part should be reinforced by practical instances given by them. What is more, it is demanded to create a pleasant atmosphere in the classroom, so that students feel comfortable and relaxed. The task should be demonstrated properly, as bad presentation results in wrong performance. Teachers should also develop a good relationship with the learners, who must feel a kind of support in the teacher, apart from that, the learners have to remember about the rules previously set and how to obey them. The language classes should be as interesting as possible for the learners; otherwise they can easily get bored. What goes without saying, teachers should

promote learners' autonomy and encourage them to make some tasks on their own. The learning process has to be personalised, what means it should refer to students' preferences and experiences. Thus, the learner's goal orientedness should be increased, so that they know what are the aims of the learning process; besides that the learners should learn not only the target language but also the target language culture. It allows for better understanding of various language issues which are different from the mother tongue.

While concluding this survey of approaches to make target language learners' motivation as strong and vivid as possible one more point has to be mentioned: what appears the most important while attempting to gain the desired educational goals, it is to closely follow the students' interests and needs. Although one's adjustment of the teaching syllabus to the students' interests always results in keeping their level of motivation on the proper level, it is not an easy task to do that; nevertheless, as Harmer (1998) assures both L2 teachers and learners, the practical realization of such a state is achievable, the right attitude to attain it being the key.

3. A few words on the target language course-books

There is no doubt that a teacher plays the crucial role in the classroom and exerts influence on the students' attitude and motivation towards the foreign language. What is more the teacher's decisions largely determine students' future whether they will continue language education or stop it when completing their school. One of the most important decisions that clearly determine learners' future appears to be appropriate selection of educational tools, one of them being a course-book.

In many countries a course-book appears to be the most basic and obligatory educational element, included in a country's foreign language syllabus, where some particular content of a course-book used at certain level of education is specified. Most, if not all, language course-book publishers outdistance each other in enhancing the layout of the course-books published by them. To make the books more motivating, such components like pictures, attractive topics, jokes, interesting and modern layout of information and/or the selection of colours are used. While meeting the educational requirements set by the core-syllabi and officially approved by the people responsible for the level and the forms of national education in a given country, course-books are expected to look inviting and attractive for potential users. In this moment a question concerning the issue of motivation ought to be raised. Does the fact that course books include all these elements make them more motivating for the students?

The answer is not always positive, as the content of many course-books is often not fully relevant to the students' needs and interests. Even if a course-book can be well and attractively designed, what remains is the teacher's role to use it skilfully, so that the students are actively involved in the lesson. Such an expectation demands from teachers to prepare themselves for the classes, to design the lessons delivered to the learners carefully, to make the lessons interesting and accepted by the learners. As in

the contemporary school it is not always easy to do it, (mostly as it is hard to find enough time for such careful preparation of the lessons), many course-book publishers offer help in the form of teacher books which, apart from containing propositions of conducting the course-book included lessons during the whole school year, also offer a rich collection of additional materials, like extension topics for more advanced students or consolidation tasks for those, who have problems with particular topics. At the same time it has to be said that although teacher books offer a wide variety of solutions which can be used in the classroom, they effectively hamper (not to say kill) many creative moves and/or possibilities of language teachers; following the eternal rule of the least effort, why to invent some attractive, and possibly easily accepted topic-connected task by oneself if there are many supposedly educationally useful ready-made propositions, waiting for the teachers in the teacher books.

Among important advantages of the course-books there can be found their predictability, as using it allows both learners and teachers to know the plan of the learning, as well as the amount of material expected to demand from the students during the whole school year; a course-book is also easy to follow for both, the learner and the teacher; each unit is consistent and balanced if it comes to the four skills' areas, what allows for some amount of guided learner autonomy in the whole process of target language learning. Thus, course-books are thought to be practical as they contain ready-made activities; they also allow teachers to save time, if it comes to lesson planning and designing tests as each course book has additional testing materials for learners and teachers.

If it comes to the disadvantages, many course-books are reported to be at fault to contain too many 'questions and answers' tasks, which make a course-book focused on testing, what can be boring as well (as grossly demotivating) for students. Harmer (2001) notices that constant corrections of learners by teachers, can be harmful for the students' fluency. What is more, many reading comprehension tasks do not present appropriate and realistic language models, what can hamper students' language development. Following the observation offered by Scrivener ((2010), the kind of predictability and sameness which is repeated in every unit of a course-book may result in the appearance of boring students. In turn, Ur (2007) claims that the grammar explanations which are often scanty and insufficient, may not offer enough practice and input information for the students who need more time to cover the topic.

4. Research objectives

The designed study is aimed at finding the influence of the course-book content on learners' motivation; we are interested in the discovery of these elements included in a course-book that may be labelled to be motivating (or demotivating) for them. Apart for that we are interested in the establishment of the teacher's attitude towards the course books (and teacher books) they use as far as students' motivation is concerned. Finally we would like to find out whether they perceive the course-books (as well as the

teacher books) as useful and helpful educational tools, in this way being willing to use both of them, or whether they prefer using different language teaching materials (their own individually designed materials included).

4.1 Research questions

The research questions raised by us can be formulated as follows:

- What elements included in the course-books motivate target language learners towards learning English and which ones can be found to be demotivating? Which of these elements make students work the most and the least efficiently?
- Are the current course-books sufficiently motivating for students?
- Are the teachers satisfied with the contents of the course-books they are using? Do they cover all the elements from these course-books? If not, which elements are omitted?
- Do teachers follow course-book adjoined teacher books? Do teacher book remain the only source for planning lessons? Are they recognized as the basis for the lessons designed by the teachers? Do they consider them as useful tools if it comes to motivating students?

4.2. Research procedures

The project involves two stages of the research. The first one is a survey conducted among elementary school teachers (both in Poland and Slovakia), whereas the second one is the course book analysis.

As far as the questionnaire is concerned it was conducted among 64 elementary school teachers who were mostly interviewed via the Internet website, with but a few instances of information gained on the basis of real face-to-face contact. The teachers were asked about the course book they use; what elements are considered by them as motivating and demotivating for students (each of the specified element was to be assessed by the polled teachers on the three-level scale); how they perceive the course-book they use; whether the course-books used by them increase students motivation and bring satisfaction to the teacher. They were also questioned how they use the course book and teacher book, and whether they perceive the latter as a useful tool when motivating students. The basic model for our questionnaire was the questionnaire used in the research conducted by O'Sullivan (1990).

If it comes to the second stage of our research, it rested upon a descriptive analysis of some of the course-books indicated by polled teachers as the ones most frequently used in the classroom. As it turned out, the course-books taken into examination were *Evolution Plus 1 & 2* and *Steps Forward 1 & 2*, both of them being the course-books designed for elementary school children. During their examination we also applied the criteria proposed by A. O'Sullivan (1990) during the research carried out by her. In this way the following aspects were examined: presentation; incentive; layout, variety, density, accessibility; expectancy. Apart from these, our analysis also

included the features indicated by the teachers in the survey as either very significant to learners' motivation, or seriously unhelpful and demotivating.

5. Results

The results obtained in the research allowed us to answer the research questions. If it comes to the first one, among the elements which have appeared motivating for students, there can be enumerated the following ones: topics related to students' interests (85,9%), presentation of everyday situations (85,9%), use of realia and flashcards (81,3%), role play and conversation work (76,6%), tasks in the multimedia form (76,6%), and tasks which students can relate to themselves (70,3%). Out of the two leading items, the most motivating element appeared to be the topics related to students' interests; this result can be justified by the fact that when students' attention is drawn to something they are interested in, they are more likely to work and engage than when offering relatively boring and monotonous topics and exercises. Another element highly ranked in the research appeared to be the presentation of everyday situations that was indicated by the polled teachers as the one of the greatest importance to students' motivation. The claim that largely outperformed other claims raised by the teachers was that the students are more likely to cooperate when they see that the exercises are meaningful and can be referred to everyday life. All the elements, together with the results found, can be found in Table 1 below.

Item	Very significant to learner's motivation	Averagely significant	Not very significant
Presentation of everyday situations	85,9 %	4,7%	9,4%
Colorful illustrations	60,9%	39,1%	0%
Role play and conversation work	76,6%	18,8%	4,7%
Use of realia and flashcards	81,3%	14,1%	4,7%
Reading texts	23,4%	56,3%	20,3%
Songs	45,3%	53,1%	1,6%
Pair work/group work	53,1%	32,8%	14,1%
Quizzes	42,2%	57,8%	0%
Tasks in the multimedia form	76,6%	23,4%	0%
Topics related to students' interests	85,9%	9,4%	4,7%
Identification of the objectives and outcomes	51,6%	34,3%	14,1%
Tasks which students can relate to themselves	70,3%	25%	4,7%
Explanation in Mother Tongue	28,1%	37,5%	34,4%

Table 1: Specification of the research results: course-book contents vs. learner's motivation (own elaboration)

Apart from the course-book elements which appeared to be motivating for the learners we also looked for the ones which demotivated them (see Table 2 below). Here, the top of the list of the elements found as demotivating by the polled teachers looks as follows: long units, texts and dialogues (60,9%); boring and unclear presentation of verbs (57,7%); unclear grammar sections (56,3%); problems with „natural” voice speed accent and clarity on recordings (56,3%); and finally repetitive exercises with no perceived point (48,4%). As it appears, what was discovered by the teachers as most motivating for their learners was the length of the units, texts and dialogues they were to deliver to the learners.

This might form a point of surprise that ought to require attentive analysis. There is obviously no reason to not believe in the indications offered by the teachers; after all they are the closest contacts with their learners able to observe their reactions and behaviours. On the other hand, however, the length of a topic, when interestingly designed and presented in the classroom may not be demotivating to the learners at all. Quite the contrary, following the general results of the research done by Gardner and Lambert (1972), if only (child) learners have found some relative amount of fun in the topic they have been requested to take part in, they may get easily involved in it, often forgetting about the amount of time spent on the issue.

Item	Seriously unhelpful and demotivating	Moderately disadvantageous	Producing no noticeably adverse effects
Repetitive exercises with no perceived point	48,4%	32,8%	18,8%
Long units, texts and dialogues	60,9%	39,1%	0%
Unclear grammar sections	56,3%	37,5%	6,3%
Boring and unclear presentation of verbs	57,8%	37,5%	4,7%
Lack of Mother Tongue explanation or translation	23,4%	62,5%	14,1%
Problems with “natural” voice speed, accent and clarity on recordings	56,3%	32,8%	10,9%
Out of date topics	25%	65,6%	9,4%
Overcrowded pages	37,5%	46,9%	15,6%

Table 2: Percentage level of handbook-based learner motivation (own elaboration)

As far as the second research question is concerned, according to the teachers’ responses (see Table 3), the majority of them consider the course-books they currently use as motivating for their students (70,3%). The analysis of the course books allows to state that they contain most of the elements specified by the polled teachers as motivating; in respect to the first of the course-books i.e. “Evolution Plus” the general

impression was positive; the whole book not only looks inviting and attractive, but also offers plenty of language-relevant information in a nice and comprehensible form. The only drawbacks that could be spotted there (indicted by many of the researched teachers as well) are some over-crowded units or pages and the lack of multimedia form of the course-book exercises. A situation like this forces the teachers to base their teaching efforts on the classical educational forms of performance, many of them might appear boring and monotonous to the learners. If it comes to the second course-book, i.e. "Steps Forward", one of the most often specified advantages was the course-book clarity, often paired with a large variety of exercises; on the other hand, many of the teachers complained about poor accessibility of the Teacher Book, as well as Many of the remaining elements that make the whole process of language deliverance simpler for both the teacher and learners i.e. the time spent by them on goal and lesson outcome stating activities, as well as the use of possible multimedia, realia and flashcards.

Teachers' responses	Frequency	%
Stating increased learners' motivation	45	70,3
Produced no measurable difference	19	29,7
Total	64	100,0

Table 3: Teachers' opinions on the course-books used by them (own elaboration)

The obtained results show that teachers are mostly satisfied with the contents of the course-books they are using, as 62,2% claimed they were fairly satisfied, and less than a half (37,5%) expressed they high level of satisfaction when asked about the book they used (Table 4). There were no respondents who claimed that they were not satisfied with their course-books they teach. The results seem to indicate that either the course-books selected by the teachers are the ones that like teaching from or they are happy about the course-books because of some other unrevealed reasons. This assertion has to be raised because of the teachers' earlier claims that the second of the proposed course-books does not offer easy access to the Teacher Books, nor many of the remaining teaching accessories.

Teachers' responses	Frequency	%
Very satisfied	24	37,5
Fairly satisfied	40	62,5
Total	64	100,0

Table 4: Teachers' satisfaction with the course-book contents (own elaboration)

When asked about detailed assessment of the course-books they are using as well as production of the reasons which helped them in the formulation of the general opinion (i.e. very satisfied - fairly satisfied - not satisfied at all) of the course-books we presented above, many of the investigated teachers were still able to produce the elements these course-books did not meet at all, or partly. Apart from that, many teachers found some of the elements actually appearing in the course-books either redundant, or not fully meeting their educational plans. Among the ones which were commonly skipped by the

teachers there were indicated: repetitive exercises; too easy or too difficult tasks; unclear grammar sections; or the topics assessed as out-dated. It is worth noticing that many of the items specified here had also been found as the ones demotivating for the students. (Table 5)

One more aspect we were interested in was the way the teachers co-operate with their course-books. In other way, we wanted to discover how far they were willing to be dependent/independent on the suggestions they could find in the course-books. The obtained results show that teachers do not stick strictly to the Teacher Books while teaching, as almost the whole group of the respondents (90,6%) answered this question negatively. We also found out that it were Teacher Books which were helpful to indicate the teachers which types of exercises could be skipped by them; the ones mentioned by them as mostly skipped were the following ones: repetitive exercises, too easy or too difficult tasks, unclear grammar sections or out of date topics. The decision to skip a given exercise was reported to have been taken after many of the polled teachers had discovered what the exercise was about. Consequently, it has to be observed that these were mostly the elements pointed out by them earlier as demotivating for students.

Teachers' responses	Yes (+)	No (-)
Do you cover all the elements from the course-book while teaching?	27 (42,2%)	37(57,8%)
Do you stick strictly to the Teacher Book while teaching?	6 (9,4%)	58 (90,6%)
Do you consider it as a useful tool for motivating students?	42 (65,5%)	22 (34,4%)
Is the Teacher Book the only source for planning the lessons?	3 (4,7%)	61(95,3%)

Table 5: Teachers' attitude to the course-book usability (own elaborations)

The final issue we would like to find out was strictly connected with the Teacher Book and its possible function in the process resulting in pro-language motivation of the students (Table 5). More than a half of the teachers (65,5%) stated that they considered the Teacher Book as a useful tool for motivating students; at the same time they mostly indicated (90,6%) that they did not consider it as the most important teaching instrument during a language lesson. Therefore, a question concerning the opinion teachers have as to various lesson motivating elements ought to be raised. If it were not Teacher Book-modified course-book contents, could that mean that it might be teachers' individual and original suggestions that function in the most useful pro-language motivating way? If that was so, what motivating function could be assigned to a Teacher Book in the whole process of positive involvement of the learners in various language activities? The correctness of this assumption can be partly indicated by the results of the fourth question asked here, where almost all polled teachers (95,3%) declared that Teachers Books are not the only source used by them when planning their lessons.

6. Conclusions

The research we did was meant to consider four important issues that related to the whole process of foreign language learning/teaching process. First of all we wanted to learn whether generally currently observed course-books (especially these generally accepted and used by language teachers) are sufficiently motivating for students.

Secondly, we wanted to discover these elements included in the course-books that do motivate/demotivate target language learners towards learning English. Additionally we were interested in the establishment of these elements which make students work the most, as well as the least efficiently.

Third of all, as the teacher-learner syndrome still remains most salient one in the whole process of education, we were interested in finding out whether language teachers are generally satisfied with the contents of the course-books they are using. Additionally we wanted to learn whether they cover all the elements from these course-books (and if not which elements are omitted). The findings are diversified here. On the one hand, they mostly claimed their satisfaction with the course-books they were using, indicating that the material and the pictures found there could often function as pro-language motivating elements; on the other one, however, they also revealed that it is them mostly who select the teaching contents while designing their lessons. This observation may mean that, together with the help of the Teacher Books they tend to consult quite often, there occurs some form of intuitive guessing as far as the possible attraction of the selected material (and thus rise in the students' motivation) is concerned. Regretfully, students themselves appear to be hardly ever requested to present their opinions here.

The final issue we were interested in concerned Teacher Books, normally being included into foreign language teaching/learning sets as their inseparable element. We wanted to learn about the following issues: whether language teachers follow the Teacher Books adjoined to course-books (and if yes, how important such Teacher Books are for them); whether Teacher Books remain the only (or at least, the basic) source for lessons planning activities carried out by these teachers; and, finally, whether the teachers consider Teacher Books as useful and helpful tools if it comes to pro-language student motivation procedures.

The answers are diversified and even surprising in some cases. As to the first aspect, the teachers mostly decided that it is mostly course-books themselves that appear to be quite useful when motivating students to get involved in various target language processes; on condition, however, that are wisely applied. In other words, it means that language lessons can be interesting for the learners when course-books are included in them, but the selection of the topics offered to the learners is to be performed (possibly in a careful and tactful way) by the teachers themselves. In this moment a remark is to be presented: following the observations offered, among others, by Strevens (1990), Dörnyei (2001), Ellis (2008), or Saemann (2009), if only one wishes to have their learners duly motivated, one must not forget that what matters a lot here are

the learners' personal interests, hobbies and/or spheres of particular affection. It is then a learner's personal attitude towards a topic that is to be taken into account when one pays attention towards their pro-language motivation. A learner, whose attitude towards a topic is (approximately) negative, or even not fully positive (because of any reason), will never strongly respond with their motivation to actively participate in the lesson. As it seems, and what has already been hinted at above, the most popular and preferred motivational path the polled teachers appeared to follow was the one where their learners' interests were diminished to the (but – as it seems - still subjectively accepted) necessary minimum.

If it comes to what elements included in the course books are motivating and perform - in many cases – truly demotivating functions, the polled teachers indicated that what mostly motivates language students are the presentations of everyday situations, the application of role plays and the production of conversation-based stage work. Apart from that, the students were found to be highly lesson-involved when various multimedia-based tasks and/or topics related to the students' interests and tasks which students could discover as being mentally close to themselves were being performed. On the other hand, as the teachers stated that the most demotivating features in the whole process of L2 deliverance are long units, text and dialogues, unclear grammar sections and overcrowded pages, as well as repetitive exercises with no perceived points, boring and unclear presentation of verbs, problems with “natural” voice speed, accent and clarity on the recordings, it was observed that many of such and/or similar topics, albeit commonly observed to occur in the assessed course-books, were still often offered to the learners, mostly because their teachers were not able to either design (and, subsequently, suggest) an activity supposedly more attractive, or because – up to a point - lulled by the Teacher Book assertions, they simply decided they could take a risk and find out how well their students would accept such a form of lessons activity.

This also seems to be one of the reasons many of the polled teachers claimed they were satisfied with the content of the course-books they use; however, it does not mean that they claimed they did cover all the elements included in them. It may indicate the fact that teachers do not strict themselves to using the course books as the only source when teaching, but they are likely to search for other materials which have also been recognized as being supposedly beneficial for the students.

Generally, the results show that teachers use Teacher Books, not treating them as the first and/or the only source of information how to design (or deliver) a lesson, but that more than a half of them consider them as a useful and helpful tool informing them about probable sources of motivation for the students they teach. At the same time, however, it has to be stated that they mostly do not recognize Teacher Books as the only student-motivating source when planning lessons; many of them admitted they often look for (and/or use) other sources while teaching.

As far as Teacher Books are concerned, it was indicated that teachers often use them as the first (and most easily accessed) student-motivating source more; it is only

after they have consulted the info found there and being not fully satisfied with the outcomes found there many teachers (following the poll results, more than a half of them) start considering other sources as useful and probable tools able to motivate their students. When planning their lessons, many teachers admitted they look for and use other (i.e. out-of-Teacher-Book) sources while teaching. Therefore, it can be stated that although teachers perceive Teacher Books as relatively motivating tools, thus making an attempt to implement other resources into the classroom.

It can be concluded that the current course-books contain the elements which are motivating for students and are perceived by teachers as useful enough when an attempt to motivate students has been made; however, this fact does not determine the way the teachers use them, as they claim they do not cover the all the topical issues included in them. Similarly, Teacher Books, enclosed to a series of course-books, albeit also recognized as helpful, when it comes to motivating the learners, are not exclusively used in the classroom, as teachers often look for other materials and sources. This is, mostly, when their creative approach to L2 teaching can be observed; they use their creativity in order to find out the most appropriate material for their learners, in many cases not relying only on the publisher's suggestions (they seem to recognize them as an obligatory form of advertising slang). Thus, they find course-books (as well as adjoined Teacher Books) as this form of their daily educational activity that duly helps increase the students' motivation, being generally satisfied with the items they use.

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References

1. Atkinson, J. & Feather, N. (eds.), (1965), *A theory of achievement motivation*, New York: John Willey and Sons, Inc.
2. Covington, M. (1992), *Making the grade: A self – worth perspective on motivation and school reform.*, New York, Cambridge University Press;
3. Dailey, A. (2009), Key motivational factors and how teachers can encourage motivation in their students. Retrieved from: <http://www.birmingham.ac.uk/Documents/college-artslaw/cels/essays/secondlanguage/DailySLAKeyMotivationalFactorsandHowTeachers.pdf> [May 31, 23:20]
4. Deci, E, & Ryan, R. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. New York: Plenum;
5. Dörnyei, Z. (1998), Motivation in second and foreign language learning, [in:] *Language Teaching* , 3, 31, pp 117 – 135;

6. Dörnyei, Z. (2001), *Motivational Strategies in the language classroom*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, p. 117;
7. Gardner, R. C., & Lambert, W. E. (1972). *Attitudes and motivation in second language learning*. Rowley, MA: Newbury House.
8. Ellis, R. (2008), *Second Language Acquisition*. New York, Oxford University Press;
9. Graham W. & Weiner B. (1996), *Theories and principles of motivation*. Available on: Retrieved from:
http://www.unco.edu/cebs/psychology/kevinpugh/motivationproject/resources/graham_weiner96.pdf [May 31, 22:45]
10. Harmer, J. (1998), *How to teach English*, Essex, Longman;
11. Harmer, J. (2001), *The Practice of English Language Teaching*, Essex, Longman;
12. Heider, F. (1958). *The Psychology of Interpersonal Relations*. New York: Wiley.
13. Huitt, W. (2001), *Motivation to learn – an overview.*, Valdosta State University;
14. Hull, C. (1943), *Principles of behaviour*, New York, Appleton – Century – Press;
15. Kelley, H. H. (1967). Attribution theory in social psychology. In D. Levine (ed.), *Nebraska Symposium on Motivation* [Vol.15, pp. 192-238]. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press;
16. Lewin, K. (1939). Field Theory and Experiment in Social Psychology. In *American Journal of Sociology*. 44 (6): pp. 868–896;
17. O’Sullivan, A.V. (1990), *The foreign language course book: a study of its role in learner motivation.*, University of London Institute of Education Press, London;
18. Rotter, J. B. (1966). Generalized expectancies for internal versus external control of reinforcement. In *Psychological Monographs*, 80.
19. Scrivener, J. (2010) *Learning teaching. The essential guide to English language teaching*. Macmillan, London.
20. Stevens, P. (1990), *Teaching English as an international language*, London: Pergamon Institute of English;
21. Saeman, B. (2009) *Motivation in second language acquisition*, München, Grin Verlag;
22. Ur. P. (2007), *A course in language teaching; practice and theory*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge;
23. Werbińska, D (2014), *Learning from Retired Language Teachers’ Biographies: A Research Proposal (pp. 57 – 74)*. In Pawlak, M. (ed.) *Classroom-Oriented Research*, London, Springer;
24. Williams M. & Burden R. (1997), *Psychology for language teachers*, New York, Cambridge University Press.

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